

1 Age-related Differences in Delta-Beta Phase-Amplitude Coupling in Autistic

2 Individuals

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21 HIGHLIGHTS

- 22 • Higher delta-beta PAC in the resting-stage EEG of autistic adults that met the thresholds
23 compared to non-autistic adults.
- 24 • Positive correlation between delta-beta PAC and restrictive and repetitive behaviours in the
25 left frontal and central regions.
- 26 • Positive correlation between delta-beta PAC and ADHD traits in autism reflected in the right
27 frontal brain region.

28 ABSTRACT

29 **Objective:** We aim to investigate the relationship between the core symptoms of autism, anxiety
30 levels, and ADHD traits, and a non-autism-specific, neurophysiological metric, the Delta-Beta
31 phase-amplitude coupling (PAC), extracted from the resting-state EEG for autistic and non-autistic
32 populations across three different age groups (children, adolescents, and adults).

33 **Methods:** We analyze the eyes-open resting-state EEG of 371 individuals. We applied a phase de-
34 biasing PAC algorithm expected to result in a more accurate PAC estimate than other PAC
35 methodologies available in the literature.

36 **Results:** In the adult group, we found a significant increase of the delta-beta PAC in the autistic
37 subgroup who met the ADOS-2/ADI-R threshold compared to non-autistic individuals. The
38 differences seem age-specific since we found no statistically significant differences in the children
39 and adolescent populations. Moreover, we found a significant positive correlation with the
40 restricted and repetitive behaviours score of the ADOS-2 diagnostic instrument and with ADHD
41 hyperactivity/impulsivity in the entire autistic cohort.

42 **Conclusions:** The neurophysiological differences we found only in the autistic individuals that
43 meet the thresholds also point out the need for future studies that look for autistic neurodiverse
44 subgroups beyond age.

45 **Significance:** The delta-beta dPAC may potentially serve as a severity biomarker in the autistic
46 population.

47

48 **Keywords:** Phase-Amplitude Coupling, autism, EEG, resting-state

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70 INTRODUCTION

71 Autistic populations are characterized by core non-normative patterns in interaction and
72 communication, repetitive and restrictive behaviours, and sensory atypicalities (American
73 Psychiatric Association, 2013). The investigation of brain differences in structure and function
74 specific to autistic populations has been challenging due to the small size of the existing
75 unreplicated studies, the heterogeneity among individuals, and the lack of specificity of
76 neurophysiological features (Morris-Rosendahl, 2020), especially in the resting-state EEG
77 (electroencephalography) (Dede, 2023). These facts encourage us to look for new features, non-
78 autism-specific, that can characterise other disorders with traits that can also be present in autism,
79 such as anxiety, impulsivity (e.g., from ADHD-related traits), repetitive behaviours, and social
80 difficulties. Indeed, mental health and disorders emerge from complex interactions among
81 biological, psychological, and cultural factors, which do not respect specific diagnostic boundaries
82 but are continuous across multiple diagnoses (Dalglish, 2020). Thus, we hypothesize that looking
83 for non-autism-specific features may reveal additional information about the autistic core
84 symptoms and other autistic traits.

85 One potential instrument to achieve this goal is the usage of EEG since it provides a direct
86 and non-invasive measure of brain function. In the EEG signals, irregularities can manifest at
87 different time scales and affect oscillations at different frequencies (Kesebir, 2019). Synchronous
88 changes in the membrane polarisation of neuronal assemblies generate high and low-frequency
89 oscillations. High-frequency oscillations reflect local cortical information processing, whereas
90 low-frequency oscillations reflect neural connectivity across more extensive cortical networks
91 (Salimpour, 2019). The tempo-spatial relationship of such oscillations at different frequencies can
92 be characterized by cross-frequency coupling in the EEG signals, such as the phase-amplitude

93 coupling (PAC). PAC quantifies the coupling of the phase of low-frequency oscillations with the
94 amplitude of high-frequency oscillations. Deficits in PAC have been associated with a variety of
95 conditions, non-specific to autistic populations, such as schizophrenia, Alzheimer's disease,
96 Parkinson's, ADHD, and anxiety (e.g., Hirano, 2018; Poza, 2017; An, 2020; Miller, 2019; Liu,
97 2022).

98 Some PAC rhythms have also been studied in autism. For instance, autistic participants
99 have exhibited greater PAC between theta phase and gamma power than neurotypical individuals,
100 and other autistic participants have exhibited increased PAC between alpha and gamma
101 oscillations (Peck, 2022). However, other autistic participants have exhibited specific regional
102 decreases as well as increases in PAC between alpha and gamma oscillations (Port, 2019). To our
103 knowledge, all autism-related studies have looked at PAC rhythms involving the gamma EEG
104 power. However, such coupling relationships are seldom robust due to the large effect of muscle
105 artifacts, especially in the gamma band (e.g., Muthukumaraswamy, 2013), which presents the
106 lowest amplitude in the EEG spectrum. This could be the reason for the inconsistencies across
107 them.

108 In this study, we explore the delta-beta PAC that is less prone to muscle artifacts and
109 reflects top-down cortical-subcortical interactions during affective processes (Knyazev, 2007;
110 Morillas-Romero et al., 2015) that are of interest in the study of emotion regulation, emotional
111 states and traits (e.g., Kesebir, 2019; Schutter & Knyazev, 2012) that could be related to autistic
112 traits and core symptoms. Delta-beta PAC has also been associated with higher levels of stress
113 (Brooker, 2016). The strength of delta-beta PAC was found to be associated with an impulsivity
114 state in the left frontal regions in bipolar disorder patients (Kesebir, 2019). Delta-beta PAC has
115 also been correlated with a state of anxiety during early anticipation in low-socially anxious

116 individuals (Poppelaars, 2018). Lastly, an increased frontal delta-beta coupling has also been
117 associated with an increased risk of anxiety problems (Najjar, 2017).

118 The clinical and aetiological heterogeneity in the core symptoms and other traits and the
119 variability in the neurophysiological signatures in autistic populations suggest the presence of
120 population subgroups (Molloy, 2021). Specifically, little is known about whether such variability
121 is age-dependent, among other factors. Indeed, some studies addressing the age-dependency issue
122 found differences in social and executive functioning abilities across the age span (Bal, 2019;
123 Rosenthal, 2013; Gray, 2012). For instance, older autistic children seem to have greater problems
124 with working memory and organization than younger autistic children (Rosenthal, 2013).
125 Moreover, another study also showcased age-related differences in cortical thickness of the autistic
126 population under investigation (Bethlehem, 2020). This does not imply that age is the only factor
127 of variability and heterogeneity, but we focus on this factor to achieve more homogeneous and less
128 variable groups. Thus, our study is interested in investigating PAC differences in the autistic
129 population over different age groups to reduce the influence of age-related factors and explore if
130 our proposed delta-beta dPAC feature behaves differently in each age group.

131 Therefore, we investigate the delta-beta dPAC feature in the resting-state EEG as a
132 potential metric to discriminate autistic from non-autistic individuals across age groups, namely
133 children, adolescents, and adults. Specifically, we hypothesize that the autistic population presents
134 differences in the delta-beta PAC compared to the typical developing population. As in previous
135 studies the delta-beta PAC was higher with anxiety-related traits, impulsivity, and higher levels of
136 stress, we expect to find higher delta-beta dPAC values in the autistic groups, and a positive
137 correlation with the anxiety scores and the ADHD impulsivity traits, although we do not have a
138 prior hypothesis regarding which age groups should mainly present such differences. We also

139 investigate the relationship of the dPAC feature with the autistic core symptoms. We do not have
140 any prior hypothesis on the correlation between the delta-beta dPAC feature and the core
141 symptoms, thus the exploratory part of this study.

142

143 **METHODS**

144 **Population**

145 We analyzed a representative subset of the LEAP dataset (Charman, 2017) (Figure S1), which
146 contains a total of 862 participants between the ages of 6 and 30 years with IQs varying between
147 50 and 148, of which 536 have EEG (electroencephalogram). Ethical approval was obtained
148 through ethics committees at each study site. All participants or legal guardians (where applicable)
149 provided written informed consent. For further details on the recruitment of participants in this
150 study, see (Charman, 2017). From the total 862, 764 have metadata, translating into 456
151 participants with EEG and metadata. We included in the analysis only the ones with $IQ > 75$ (371
152 individuals, 221 autistic and 150 non-autistic) and at least one clean EEG epoch of 10 sec (see
153 *EEG preprocessing* section) (8 individuals were removed entirely due to less than one clean EEG
154 epoch). As when including the total autistic cohort, we did not find any significant differences in
155 any age groups, we report here only the group analyses carried out in the autistic individuals
156 (N=110) who, in addition to the clinical diagnosis, also met the ADOS-2 and ADI-R thresholds
157 for broader autism (Charman, 2017). We stratify the study population (autistic who meet the
158 thresholds and non-autistic people) in three age groups, namely children (39 non-autistic and 28
159 autistic, 9.6 ± 1.5 years, 6-12 years), adolescents (48 non-autistic and 49 autistic, 15.1 ± 1.9 years,
160 12-18 years), and adults (63 non-autistic and 33 autistic, 23.1 ± 3.2 years, 18-31 years), to
161 investigate possible age-dependent differences in the proposed metric. For the correlation

162 analysis, we used the total autistic population (N=221; see *Statistical and Correlation Analyses*
163 sections). This process is presented in Figure S1 (supplementary material).

164

165

166 **Behavioral and electrophysiological assessments**

167 The EEG was acquired in 5 sites with Brainvision, Biosemi, and Micromed systems. All
168 sites used 10-20 layout caps, with 60-64 EEG electrodes and recordings consisting of 2-min of
169 resting-state eyes open and 2 min of resting-state eyes closed (in alternating segments of 30s).

170 The behavioral assessments under consideration consisted of the ADI-R (Autism
171 Diagnostic Interview-Revised) diagnostic instrument (ADI-R social domain total score, ADI-R
172 communication domain total score, and ADI-R restrictive and repetitive behaviors total domain
173 score), the ADOS-2 (Autism Diagnostic Observation Schedule, Lord, 2012) diagnostic instrument
174 (Calibrated Severity Scores (CSS) total, social effect CSS, and restrictive and repetitive behaviors
175 CSS), the ADHD (Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder) inattentiveness score (parent report)
176 and the ADHD impulsivity score (parent report), as well as the DAWBA (Development and Well-
177 Being Assessment) anxiety score. The ADI-R and ADOS-2 scores were not administered to the
178 non-autistic or mild ID groups without autism (Charman, 2017). These scores are explained in the
179 following sections.

180

181 *ADI-R scores*

182 The ADI-R scores are among the most widely used for diagnosing autistic people (Risi, 2006).

183 The ADI-R score covers three domains, namely the social interaction domain (ADI-R social
184 domain total score – ADI_social_total), the communication domain (ADI-R communication
185 domain – ADI_communication), and the restricted and repetitive behaviours domain (ADI-R

186 restrictive and repetitive behaviors total domain score – ADI_RRB). The ADI-R scores provide
187 early developmental symptom severity information (Charman, 2017).

188

189

190 *ADOS-2 scores*

191 The ADOS-2 score is a revised, standardized measurement for diagnosing autistic people (Lord,
192 2012). The ADOS-2 provides the Calibrated Severity Score (CSS) (Gotham, 2012) that presents a
193 more valid indicator of severity compared to the raw ADOS scores. The CSS for Social Affect
194 (SA_CSS), for restricted and repetitive behaviours (RRB_CSS), and the overall total scores
195 (Total_CSS) are analyzed in this study. The ADOS-2 are observational measures of current
196 symptom severity (Charman, 2017).

197 We also used the Repetitive Behaviors Scale – Revised (RBS-R), a self-report questionnaire to
198 measure the breadth of repetitive behavior in children, adolescents, and adults with autism (Lam,
199 2007). The RBS-R provides a quantitative, continuous measure of the full spectrum of repetitive
200 behaviors.

201

202 *ADHD (Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder) inattentiveness score and the ADHD impulsivity*
203 *score.*

204 The DSM-5 rating scale of attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) measures the presence
205 of inattention and hyperactive/impulsive symptoms in the past 6 months (DSM-5). Depending on
206 age and ability level, either parent- or self-report forms were administered (Charman, 2017).

207

208 *DAWBA (Development and Well-Being Assessment) anxiety scores*

209 The DAWBA (Goodman, 2000) questionnaire is an effective diagnostic tool in clinical and
210 epidemiological settings and can capture anxiety total scores.

211

212

213 **Analyses**

214 *EEG preprocessing*

215 The EEG analyses were conducted on Matlab 2016b and Python 3.6 with in-house scripts.

216 The EEG data were pre-processed in the following way: the signals were filtered between 1 and

217 32 Hz, the ocular and muscular components were removed with ICA (fieldtrip), the channels with

218 remaining artifacts were identified and interpolated, the clean signals were re-referenced to the

219 common average, and split into trials of EO (eyes-open) (around 4 EO sequences of 30s per

220 subject) (Figure S2, supplementary material). These data were further segmented into 10-sec

221 epochs with 50% overlap. Any epochs with amplitude higher than 100uV were also considered

222 noisy and were removed from the analyses. We have included 1700 clean epochs (Non-autistic:

223 682 total clean epochs, 3.7 ± 1.33 average epochs, median = 4, Autistic: 1018 epochs, 3.7 ± 1.19

224 average epochs, median = 4). We then grouped the 61 channels into 12 brain regions of interest

225 (ROIs), namely left and right frontal, left and right central, left and right temporal, left and right

226 parietal, left and right occipital, anterior midline, and posterior midline for each epoch (Figure S2)

227 and averaged the time signals from all channels within a region to result in one signal per brain

228 region of interest.

229

230

231 *EEG feature extraction*

232 The dPAC was extracted by computing 1) the phase of the delta oscillations (1-4Hz, filtered with
233 a zero-phase Butterworth filter of order 4 for each brain region and epoch using the Hilbert
234 transform, 2) the amplitude of the beta oscillations (13-32Hz, filtered with a zero-phase
235 Butterworth filter of order 4) for each brain region and epoch using the Hilbert transform, 3)
236 computing the debiasing PAC (dPAC) (van Driel, 2015). Higher dPAC values indicate higher
237 phase-amplitude coupling between the delta and beta oscillations.

238

239 *Statistical and Correlation Analyses*

240 Statistical and correlation analyses on the electrophysiological data were performed in Matlab
241 2016b. The non-parametric Wilcoxon test was used for the pair-wise comparisons, and the non-
242 parametric Spearman partial correlation (adjusted for the age covariate) was used to estimate the
243 correlations between dPAC and behavioural assessments. Specifically, we perform the group-wise
244 comparisons between the non-autistic and autistic populations split into age groups to identify
245 case-control differences across the life span. In the correlation analysis, we use age as a continuous
246 covariate instead of splitting into three age groups. In this case, we are not interested in
247 investigating the effect of age per se, but we are interested in the dependency between delta-beta
248 dPAC and the clinical/behavioural variables. As we found in the case-control analyses that age is
249 an important factor, we adjusted for the effect of age in the correlation analysis. The False
250 Discovery Rate (FDR) algorithm (Benjamini & Hochberg, 1995) was used to correct for multiple
251 comparisons across the different brain regions in the pair-wise comparisons case or across the
252 various clinical scores of each category in the correlational analysis case. Cohen's d was estimated
253 to account for the effect sizes.

254 We also estimated the delta and beta relative EEG power for each brain region and epoch to
255 investigate whether any power changes could drive the dPAC results. We performed the same
256 statistical analyses as with dPAC to ensure that our results were not driven by the power of the two
257 oscillations under investigation but by their actual delta-beta coupling relationships.

258 Results

259 We did not obtain any significant differences in the dPAC between the non-autistic (N=150) and
260 the entire autistic cohort (N=221) in any of the age groups (Figure 1).
261

262
263 *Figure 1. PAC results for the non-autistic and autistic entire populations split into different age groups. No statistically significant*
264 *differences ($p > 0.05$) exist in any age group.*

265

266 We did obtain significant differences in the dPAC between the non-autistic (N = 150) and the
 267 autistic adults who meet the ADOS/ADI threshold (N = 110) population, correcting for 12 multiple
 268 comparisons (for the 12 brain regions under consideration) using the FDR (the three age-groups
 269 under consideration are independent). Specifically, we found that the delta-beta PAC is
 270 significantly higher in the adult autistic population who meet the ADOS-2/ADI-R threshold
 271 compared to non-autistic adults in the left frontal, midline, left and right central, temporal, and
 272 parietal lobes, as well as in the parietal midline. There were no case-control significant differences
 273 in the children and adolescents groups. These results are presented in Figure 2.

274
 275
 276 *Figure 2. PAC results for the non-autistic and autistic narrow populations split into different age groups. The asterisks indicate*
 277 *significant differences at $p < 0.05$ for values corrected for multiple comparisons using FDR.*

278

279 We estimated the Cohen's d for the adult population, the values of which are presented in Figure
280 3, for each brain region.

281
282

283

284 *Figure 3. Cohen's d value is represented in the Brain. The red colour corresponds to the maximum value, whereas the blue colour*
285 *corresponds to the minimum. The regions with the highest Cohen's d value are the anterior midline and right parietal.*

286

287 As shown in Figure 3 for almost all significant brain regions, the effect is medium to large, with

288 the largest effect appearing on the right parietal ($d=0.75$) and the anterior midline regions ($d=0.75$).

289 In Figure 4, we plot the probability distribution (normal fit) of the children's, adolescents', and

290 adults' conditions to visually inspect dPAC with age.

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292
293
294

Figure 4. A. Anterior midline and B. right parietal results for the dPAC and the probability distributions for children, adolescents, and adults (EO condition). The whiskers depict the standard error of the mean (SEM).

295
296

We hypothesized that the differences we found in the adult populations are attributed to larger brain alterations during advanced age in these populations. Indeed, there was a larger increase in the delta-beta PAC of the autistic population from childhood to adulthood ($F=2.95$, $p=0.08$), although not significant, compared to the corresponding dPAC change of the non-autistic population ($F=0.12$, $p=0.73$) (Figure 5).

300

301

302 *Figure 5. Delta-beta PAC of autistic and non-autistic individuals across age. There is a higher increase, although not significant,*
 303 *in the dPAC of the autistic population from childhood to adulthood ($F=2.95$, $p=0.08$, fitted linear regression model).*

304

305

306 *dPAC correlations with behavioral assessments in the autistic group only*

307 We analysed the partial correlation between the clinical scores and the delta-beta dPAC feature

308 of the entire autistic population ($N=221$), correcting for the effect of age, as we showed in the

309 previous section different dPAC results across the three different age groups. The FDR-corrected

310 p-values for each category (ADI-R, ADOS-2, ADHD, DAWBA) and corresponding R values

311 between each brain region and clinical score are presented in Table S1 (*supplementary material*).

312 The right frontal, left and right occipital regions were excluded from the correlation analysis, as

313 they did not yield any significant differences between the non-autistic and the autistic

314 populations that meet the thresholds. The corresponding headplots of the significant regions are

315 presented in Figure 6. The p-values have been corrected for each category, but not for each brain
 316 region. Correcting for the brain regions all significant correlations disappear.
 317

318
 319
 320 *Figure 6. Headplots of the correlations between dPAC and clinical scores. The dark points correspond to the FDR-corrected*
 321 *significant correlations ($p < 0.05$).*

322 As shown in Table S1.1 (*supplementary material*) and Figure 6, there are significant correlations
 323 in the ADOS-2 restricted and repetitive behaviour scale in the left frontal ($\rho=0.2$, $p=0.02$) and
 324 central regions ($\rho=0.18$, $p=0.045$) and a tendency in the right central ($\rho=0.15$, $p=0.12$) and left
 325 temporal regions ($\rho=0.17$, $p=0.077$). There are no significant correlations in the ADI-R scale
 326 (Table S1.2) and a significant correlation between the ADHD hyperimpulsivity score and the
 327 dPAC measure in the central left region ($\rho=0.19$, $p=0.025$) (Table S1.3). All correlations are
 328 positive, indicating that a higher dPAC delta-beta coupling in the autistic population is related to
 329 higher restricted and repetitive behaviour scores and higher hyperimpulsivity scores.

330 We also explored the dPAC correlation with the Repetitive Behaviours scale-Revised (Lam,
 331 2007), where we also found a significant correlation in the central right region ($\rho=0.19$, $p=0.012$).
 332 The correlations between the RRB_CSS and dPAC for the frontal left and central left regions are
 333 presented in Figure 7.

334
 335 *Figure 7. Correlation between the RRB_CSS scores and the dPAC in the left frontal and central regions. The headplots display the*
 336 *electrode ROIs that presented significant results (i.e., frontal left by green and central left by pink). The areas are uniformly*
 337 *coloured only for visualisation purposes.*

338
 339 *Anxiety scores*

340 In our sample, we measured the anxiety scores with the DAWBA anxiety scale. We investigated
 341 the associations between dPAC and DAWBA scores, as well as between the RRB and the
 342 DAWBA scores. We did not find any significant correlation between dPAC and anxiety scores
 343 (Table S1.4) in any brain region nor between the RRB scores and the DAWBA anxiety scores
 344 ($\rho=0.08$, $p=0.3$).

346 *Delta-beta power analyses*

347 We estimated the delta and beta power for each brain region to investigate any possible effects of
348 the power on the dPAC results. We performed the same statistical analysis as previously. There
349 are no significant differences in the delta or the beta band between the non-autistic and autistic
350 adults.

351 Regarding the correlation between the dPAC and the delta and beta bands, there is no significant
352 FDR-corrected correlation (2 components for correction: delta and beta). In contrast, there is a
353 significant correlation between the beta power and the delta-beta dPAC in the left parietal ($\rho=-$
354 0.13 , $p=0.03$) and the right occipital regions ($\rho=-0.12$, $p=0.04$).

355
356 **Discussion**

357 This study aimed to investigate the cross-frequency delta-beta coupling differences in autistic
358 individuals compared to age-matched non-autistic individuals. Additionally, the study aimed to
359 explore any relationships between such differences and the clinical or behavioural scales, shedding
360 more light on the underlying neurophysiological signatures of autistic traits related to ADHD and
361 anxiety and the autistic core symptoms, as seen from a non-autism-specific neurophysiological
362 metric point of view.

363 We found a significant increase in delta-beta PAC in the autistic adults compared to the non-
364 autistic adults in the whole brain, except in the occipital and right frontal areas. In contrast, we
365 found no significant case-control differences for the children or the adolescent groups. Increased
366 delta-beta PAC is associated with increased risk for anxiety problems (Najjar and Brooker 2016),
367 as well as with impulsivity and cyclothymic temperament scores in bipolar disorder patients
368 (Kesebir, 2019), indicating that the observed differences in the two populations may be attributed
369 to underlying mechanisms of affect- and self-dysregulation (Degnan, 2010; Phelps, 2016).

370 Additionally, it is evidenced in the literature that enhanced cortical-subcortical interactions that
371 reflect increased interregional crosstalk in delta and beta EEG bands predict increased behavioural
372 inhibition and anxiety (Schutter and Honk, 2005). The authors revealed that cortisol enhances the
373 cortical-subcortical information exchange reflected in the delta-beta coupling. The
374 interdependence of these rhythms shows steroid hormone-mediated properties associated with
375 specific brain states and behavioral outcomes of inhibition and anxiety. Moreover, (Brooker, 2016)
376 investigated the relationship between delta-beta coupling and neuroendocrine reactivity in infants
377 and showed that high-cortisol reactive infants had greater coupling than low-cortisol reactive
378 children during non-positive episodes, highlighting again the possible role of cortisol on the delta-
379 beta coupling. We also know from the literature that an increase in dPAC is associated with high
380 levels of social fear in preschoolers at frontal and central electrode sites (Phelps, 2016), as well as
381 with high levels of stress and anxiety also at frontal electrode sites (Brooker, 2016; Najjar 2017).
382 Evidence has also shown that the RRB scores are highly correlated with high levels of anxiety and
383 impairments in cognitive control (Rodgers, 2012; Black, 2017; Pickard, 2020), as well as with
384 higher levels of fear in autistic populations (Uljarevic and Evans 2017). However, in our sample,
385 we did not find any significant correlation between dPAC and the DAWBA anxiety scores in any
386 brain region nor between the RRB scores and the DAWBA anxiety scores. It is worth mentioning
387 that none of the above papers reporting associations between RRB and anxiety used the DAWBA
388 scales. Thus, further research beyond the DAWBA anxiety would be needed to identify if these
389 changes may be attributed to a difference in emotion regulation in the autistic population.

390

391 Specific core regions related to autistic phenotypes include the frontotemporal lobe, frontoparietal
392 cortex, amygdala, hippocampus, basal ganglia, and anterior cingulate cortex. The frontal lobe,

393 superior temporal cortex, parietal cortex, and amygdala are associated with impairments in social
394 behaviour, and the orbitofrontal cortex is associated with repetitive and restrictive patterns of
395 behaviour in autistic (Ha, 2015; Amaral, 2008; Adolphs, 2001; Kim, 2010; Atmaca, 2007). This
396 evidence may explain the delta-beta PAC differences we found almost everywhere in the brain,
397 although source analyses would be needed to support this further.

398

399 Although we analysed three different age groups, we only found significant differences in the adult
400 populations that meet the ADOS/ADI thresholds. As we know that the core symptoms of autistic
401 people are accompanied by neurodevelopmental changes in brain anatomy, functioning, and
402 connectivity throughout the whole lifespan (Ecker, 2015; Ha, 2015; van Rooij, 2018), we
403 hypothesize that the differences we found in the adult populations are attributed to larger brain
404 alterations during advanced age in these populations. Indeed, there was a larger increase in the
405 delta-beta PAC of the autistic population from childhood to adulthood, although not significant,
406 compared to the corresponding dPAC change of the non-autistic population. This suggests that the
407 dPAC differences in adulthood may be attributed to an increase of the underlying brain differences
408 in the autistic population and may reflect the impact of environmental effects and individual
409 differences in such effects and their interactions with the brain.

410

411 The fact that we only found differences when analysing the adult autistic population who meet the
412 ADOS/ADI-R thresholds and not in the total autistic population may be attributed to the lack of
413 clear neurophysiological boundaries that define the diagnosis or to the fact that these individuals
414 may have potentially different features to autistic adults who are meeting these thresholds or they
415 have more pronounced autistic characteristics reflected in their neurophysiological signatures.

416 Also, the fact that there is no difference in the children or adolescent groups that meet the
417 thresholds can be attributed to higher heterogeneity and neurodivergence in these groups. These
418 open the way for carrying out studies that stratify autistic individuals based on their
419 neurophysiological characteristics, creating neurodiverse groups beyond age.

420

421 Our rationale for splitting the sample into three different age groups rather than using age as a
422 covariate in the first analysis was to investigate how this metric behaves in different age groups
423 and qualitatively evaluate its performance as a potential early diagnosis or severity biomarker. In
424 the literature, many studies focus on only one age group (e.g., only children or adults), making it
425 difficult to explore how their proposed markers affect other age groups. In our case, since our
426 marker under investigation was mainly influenced by the adult population, we would recommend
427 as a next step to explore this marker as a potential severity marker of autism. Exploring three
428 different age groups also has some limitations, including the possible differential contribution to
429 the results of potential confounds.

430

431 We found that increased dPAC scores in the left frontal and central brain areas were significantly
432 correlated with higher repetitive and restrictive behaviour scores. RRBs are characterised by
433 repetition, insistence on sameness, lack of flexibility, inappropriateness, and lack of specific action
434 purpose. RRBs belong to the core symptoms of autism. Although they have not received as much
435 research attention as the social communication impairments, they affect the quality of life equally
436 and thus need further investigation (Tian, 2022). The left frontal and central increase that we found
437 in the dPAC is visually very similar to the topography of the alpha over-connectivity we see in
438 infants with autism, which is also associated with RRBs (Haartsen, 2019; Orekhova, 2014). It is

439 interesting to consider whether these signals all point to a common root of regions that may relate
440 to RRBs particularly, even though the precise nature of the atypicality is different. Indeed, many
441 studies have reported the implication of the Cortico-Striatal-Thalamo-Cortical (CSTC) circuit in
442 the presence of RRB. According to (Langen, 2011), the CSTC circuit mainly involves the
443 sensorimotor circuit, the associative circuit (i.e., the dorsolateral prefrontal loop), and the lateral
444 orbitofrontal and anterior cingulate loops. This may also explain why we found significant
445 associations between dPAC and RRB in the frontal and central regions. Thus, although dPAC has
446 not been investigated so far in the autistic population, a correlation between this metric and the
447 RRB scores may indicate severity and could further serve as a potential biomarker in this
448 population. To our knowledge, the present study is the first to report a relationship between delta-
449 beta coupling and repetitive and restrictive behaviour.

450

451 When looking at the relationship between the ADHD scores and the dPAC scores, we found a
452 significant positive correlation in ADHD hyperimpulsivity scores in the right central region.
453 Although there is not much literature to support this finding, (Kesebir, 2019) reported larger delta-
454 beta PAC related to larger impulsivity scores in bipolar disorder patients. This finding may imply
455 impulsivity traits in autistic individuals with high dPAC scores. It would be worth further
456 investigating this metric as a predictor of ADHD comorbidity in the autistic population.

457

458 We found no significant differences between the autistic and non-autistic adult populations
459 regarding delta and beta EEG power. Still, we did find a significant correlation between the beta
460 power and the delta-beta dPAC in the left parietal and the right occipital regions. However, this
461 finding can neither explain the significant differences we found in the delta-beta PAC analyses in

462 the rest of the brain regions nor the correlations of the dPAC with the clinical scores, which
463 appeared in the left frontal and central areas. Furthermore, it is noteworthy that we did not find
464 any significant difference between the autistic and non-autistic adult populations in terms of the
465 dPAC measure in the right occipital region, which indicates that the delta-beta PAC differences
466 between the two populations cannot be attributed to simple EEG power effects.

467

468 In this study, we have only analysed the eyes-open segments, as the delta-beta PAC reflects
469 anxiety-related traits, impulsivity, and higher stress levels, which are more likely to occur in a real-
470 life situation with eyes open. Additionally, an eyes-closed condition impacts physiological arousal
471 by reducing it (increase in EEG alpha band), indicating a more relaxed state (Barry et al., 2007).
472 We, thus, decided to avoid any bias that such a condition could introduce to our marker that is also
473 related to cortisol which is, in turn, related to arousal.

474

475 To conclude, we found a significant increase in the delta-beta PAC of the autistic adults who meet
476 the ADOS/ADI-R thresholds compared to the delta-beta PAC of the age-matched non-autistic
477 individuals. This increase is related to age in the autistic population, as there is a linear increase in
478 the dPAC scores with age in the autistic individuals. It is also associated with an increase in the
479 repetitive and restrictive behavioural scales of autistic individuals, especially in the left frontal and
480 central brain regions, and with an increase in the ADHD scores in the right central region. An
481 increase in dPAC may be attributed to differences reflected in restrictive and repetitive behaviours
482 and ADHD-related behaviours. It may potentially serve as a severity biomarker in the autistic
483 population, but this would need further investigation.

484

485 **Author contributions**

486

487 E.K. and A.S-F conceived the idea. E.K. analysed the data and wrote the first draft of the
488 manuscript. E.J. B.O., J.B., T.C., E.L., D.M. and A.S-F contributed to the interpretation and
489 discussion of the results and to the writing of the final manuscript. All authors read and approved
490 the final manuscript.

491

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Figure S 1. Block diagram of subject inclusion criteria.

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642 Figure S 2. EEG Pre-processing steps

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645 Table S1.1. FDR-corrected p -values of the partial correlation between the delta-beta dPAC and the clinical scores. The p -values
646 have been corrected for the correlations with the three css clinical scores but not for the brain regions.

P-values FDR-corrected and ρ	Frontal Left	Central Left	Central Right	Temporal Left	Temporal Right	Parietal Left	Parietal Right	Anterior Midline	Posterior Midline
SA_CSS									
ρ	0.03	-0.001	0.04	0.08	0.04	-0.03	-0.02	0.06	-0.04
P value	0.67	0.98	0.61	0.28	0.59	0.91	0.91	0.36	0.85
RRB_CSS									
ρ	0.2	0.18	0.15	0.17	0.11	0.06	0.027	0.13	0.08
P value	0.021	0.045	0.12	0.077	0.4	0.91	0.91	0.22	0.85
Total_CSS									
ρ	0.08	0.06	0.09	0.12	0.07	-0.008	0.008	0.096	-0.004
P value	0.44	0.58	0.33	0.14	0.46	0.91	0.91	0.29	0.95

647

648 Table S1.2. FDR-corrected p -values of the partial correlation between the delta-beta dPAC and the clinical scores. The p -values
649 have been corrected for the correlations with the 3 ADI clinical scores but not for the brain regions.

P-values FDR-corrected and ρ	Frontal Left	Central Left	Central Right	Temporal Left	Temporal Right	Parietal Left	Parietal Right	Anterior Midline	Posterior Midline
ADI_soci									
ρ	0.005	0.02	0.03	0.03	-0.008	0.02	0.04	0.02	0.07
P value	0.95	0.78	0.71	0.68	0.91	0.78	0.55	0.72	0.96
ADI_RRB									
ρ	-0.03	0.04	0.04	-0.03	-0.01	-0.02	0.06	-0.09	0.01
P value	0.95	0.78	0.71	0.68	0.91	0.78	0.55	0.63	0.96

ADI_communication	ρ	0.02	0.07	0.04	0.04	-0.01	0.04	0.05	0.03	0.003
	P value	0.95	0.78	0.71	0.68	0.91	0.78	0.55	0.72	0.96

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Table S1.3. FDR-corrected p-values of the partial correlation between the delta-beta dPAC and the clinical scores. The p-values have been corrected for the correlations with the 2 ADHD clinical scores but not for the brain regions.

P-values FDR-corrected and R		Frontal Left	Central Left	Central Right	Temporal Left	Temporal Right	Parietal Left	Parietal Right	Anterior Midline	Posterior Midline
ADHD_inattentive	ρ	-0.02	0.08	0.13	-0.009	0.008	-0.005	0.03	-0.05	-0.02
	P value	0.77	0.52	0.09	0.91	0.92	0.95	0.74	0.52	0.84
ADHD_hyperimpulsive	ρ	0.13	0.19	0.02	0.03	0.05	0.09	-0.05	0.02	0.08
	P value	0.18	0.025	0.91	0.92	0.95	0.46	0.52	0.79	0.58

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Table S1.4. FDR-corrected p-values of the partial correlation between the delta-beta dPAC and the DAWBA clinical scores.

P-values FDR-corrected and R		Frontal Left	Central Left	Central Right	Temporal Left	Temporal Right	Parietal Left	Parietal Right	Anterior Midline	Posterior Midline
DAWBA anxiety	ρ	-0.02	0.0005	-0.03	-0.07	-0.006	0.1	0.02	0.05	0.04
	P value	0.77	0.52	0.9	0.91	0.92	0.95	0.74	0.52	0.84

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